

Rules for Heating Tactile Tiles

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Abstract:

The article analyzes the correct application of tactile coatings for use in urban infrastructure, buildings and structures.

Key words: tactile surfaces, vital functions, less mobile citizens, full presence, periodicity, infrastructure, mnemonic schemes, public buildings, adaptation, spatial orientation, navigators, and mobile applications.

Tactile materials serve as a passive technical warning tool that warns visually impaired people of obstacles and dangerous places in their direction - on public sidewalks, communication roads in residential and industrial buildings, public buildings and open access structures to public places. It is used to determine the movement paths during the use of vehicles .

There are several types of tactile-visual marking:

- Tactile Tile
- Tactile indicators
- Tactile tape
- Highlight (tactile marking) are s.

Tactile polymer concrete tiles interior and external spaces laying down for is a universal solution . Such a tile is har how place adaptation for answer gives , because it is up to several tons has been daily to cargo endure giving strength increased as well as long service to do extended the term

Polymer concrete coatings.

Tactile granite tiles - such tiles are designed for installation in rooms with high traffic. It is possible to create a safe environment in buildings and structures for the blind and disabled, and provide immediate adaptation of public, street, and courtyard spaces for visually impaired people. In cases of use in the interiors of public buildings, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the materials covering the floor of the buildings. Otherwise, floor coverings with tactile materials will cause difficulties in the movement of disabled people.

Granite coatings.

Tactile ceramic tiles are designed for adaptation of rooms with high traffic for persons with partial or complete loss of vision. Tactile concrete tiles are used to mark special zones in public places (passages, traffic lights, barriers, etc.), to ensure the unhindered movement of groups of citizens with reduced mobility. . Street tiles are usually made of concrete, which allows it to be used in various weather conditions, and is resistant to frost. It is relative cheap for the price have , durable and to several tons of cargo endure give takes In addition to special installations at bus stops, there are contrasting tactile concrete tiles warning signs, in cases where road construction works are fully operational, public transport will be easy to use.

Concrete coatings.

Tactile polyurethane tile is a convenient tool for the interior of any building, and when using it, special attention is paid to the square meters of the building.

Polyurethane coatings.

It is recommended to use PVC coverings for the interior of the building where the flow of traffic is not too high.

PVC coatings

Tactile self-adhesive coating is suitable as a means of temporary adjustment of medium and low-traffic rooms. Tactile indicators are special devices used to mark the way for the blind. Indicators are made in the form of cones and lines and are used indoors and outdoors, as well as in places where it is not possible to lay tactile tiles. Cones usually serve to identify dangerous areas, such as the edges of platforms, while lines make it easier to determine the vector of movement.

Tactile indicators:

Polyurethane tactile indicators are made of good quality and at a very high cost.

Polyurethane tactile indicators.

PVC indicators can be used in small areas. Area floor coverings are required to be in contrasting colors with PVC coverings. In emergency situations, if the surface of the floor coverings is made of smooth materials, the indicator forms reliefs on it.

PVC indicators.

In addition, there are indicators made of stainless steel, aluminum, and brass materials. Covering for public and civil buildings and administrative buildings is selected on the basis of construction standards.

The infrastructure of modern countries and megacities is very complex and extensive, so accurately understanding the direction of a person in the urban environment is a complex process. In developed countries, in the process of conducting scientific research and research, practical projects are also implemented in the process of solving the problems of organizing facilities in urban infrastructures in relation to the type of disabled people. Since every country has its own internal regulations and building codes, development processes are different. It is estimated that 15% of the population in Uzbekistan are people with various disabilities. As the infrastructure of the city of Tashkent becomes more complex, difficulties arise for the blind and wheelchair users, as well as for the elderly. When properly coated as a guiding material for the visually impaired, tactile surfaces can be used in any area.

overcome various obstacles. As a result of the research, when we analyzed the streets of our city, some of them were paved with tactile materials or traffic-directing pavements in contrasting color. For example, tactile materials are partially covered at the intersections of Shota Rustaveli, Shakhrisabz, and Independence streets and pedestrian walkways. During the movement, small architectural forms, such as a trash can, two flower pots, are placed directly on the tactile material. Although such cases are small defects, they are encountered in many cases.

Covering the streets of Tashkent with tactile materials.

Tactile materials A warning sign in the form of a bump on the part of the underground and surface pedestrian movement from the objects of the urban infrastructure covered as The coating is placed along the entire corridor, and on the first step of the stairs. The width of the covering should be 80 cm. 80X80 cm pavements at intersections of main streets, as well as tactile coverings at the main entrances of various socially important objects. Pedestrian movement corridors will be established in the objects located along the main street, and these corridors will be covered with a tactile coating on the right side of the building. Ramps with a slope of no more than 5% are placed in each building . The dimensions, features of use and individual adoption of the above-mentioned coverings for any object are necessarily based on construction standards. In developed countries, there are standards that can fully analyze and determine the dimensions of each coating, and in order to be able to use it correctly even in our new modern constructions, deep knowledge and skills are required from our specialists.

In conclusion, when designing any object, it is necessary not only to have a deep understanding of construction standards, but also to implement modern solutions that should be included in normative documents.

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